

METHODS AND RESULTS OF THE COLOR SPECTROMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE GRAPE BIOACTIVE POLYPHENOLIC DRINK "GRAPE ELIXIR"

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Abstract. Grape elixir is a product made from pure grape juice with no added ingredients that is high in antioxidants, vitamins, and minerals. The study evaluates the colorimetric indicators and the grape polyphenolic drink "Grape elixir" obtained from the most valuable technical black and red grape varieties, including Rangdor, Saperavi, Cabernet Sauvignon, Khindogni, Pinot Noir, Maysky Cherny, and Magarachsky grown in Uzbekistan's Tashkent region. Additional parameters such as conductivity and pH of the technology used to produce the ecologically friendly grape elixir "Grape elixir" are also evaluated.

Keywords: grapes, elixir, juice, polyphenols, pH, vitamins, trans resveratrol, berry, seeds, comb, antioxidant activity.

Аннотация. Виноградный эликсир — это продукт, приготовленный из чистого виноградного сока без добавления ингредиентов, с высоким содержанием антиоксидантов, витаминов и минералов. В исследовании оцениваются колориметрические показатели и виноградный полифенольный напиток "Виноградный эликсир", полученный из наиболее ценных технических красных и черных сортов винограда, включая Рангдор, Саперави, Каберне Совиньон, Хиндоньи, Пино Нуар, Майский Черный и Магарачский, выращенных в Ташкентской области Узбекистана. Также определены дополнительные параметры, такие как электропроводность и pH технологии, используемой для производства экологически чистого виноградного эликсира "Виноградный эликсир".

Ключевые слова: виноград, эликсир, сок, полифенолы, pH, витамины, трансресвератрол, ягода, семена, гребень, антиоксидантная активность

Annotatsiya. Uzum eliksiri antioksidantlar, vitaminlar va minerallarga boy tarkibiy qismlarga ega bo'lmagan sof uzum sharbatidan tayyorlangan mahsulotdir. Tadqiqotda rangdor, Saperavi, Cabernet Sauvignon, Xindogni, Pinot Noir, Mayskiy Cherniy va Magarachskiy kabi eng qimmatbaho texnik qizil va qora uzum navlaridan olingan kolorimetrik ko'rsatkichlar va uzum polifenolik ichimlik "uzum eliksiri" baholanadi. Ekologik toza uzum eliksiri "uzum eliksiri" ni ishlab chiqarish uchun ishlatiladigan texnologiyaning o'tkazuvchanligi va pH kabi qo'shimcha parametrlar ham baholandi.

Kalit so'zlar: uzum, eliksir, sharbat, polifenollar, pH, vitaminlar, transresveratrol, berry, urug'lar, taroq, antioksidant faollik.

Introduction

The health benefits of grape polyphenols have long been known, and scientists are growing more and more interested about compounds. The goal of this study is to investigate the biochemical content and properties of a non-alcoholic, highly nutritious grape elixir made from native and introduced wine grape varieties such as Rangdor, Saperavi, Cabernet sauvignon, Khindogni Pino Noir, Mayskiy Cherniy, Magarachskiy, and Tavkveri grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan's Tashkent region.

One of the most major obstacles in Uzbekistan is the production of nutritious food. In recent years, especially during the off-season, when fruits and vegetables are grown in large quantities, there have been multiple cases of anemia, a compromised immune system, and an outbreak of chronic respiratory illnesses. This is notably visible in the pandemics of recent years. Grapes and many of its derivatives (juice, wine, elixir, raisins, molasses, and so on) are especially advantageous in terms of strengthening the human immune system. Grape products are recognized for their high biochemical content, antioxidant activity, trans-resveratrol, vitamins C and B, and sugars that are easy to digest. [3, 4, 5]. However, such grape-based products cannot appropriately serve all parts of the population. This issue can be explained by our country's social customs and age demographics. For fact, one of the fruit plants that is most frequently grown in Uzbekistan is the grapevine. In contrast to the convincing data displayed above, our republic's gross grape crop as of right now is about 1.8 million tons. [4].

Its major component is new to consumption and exports. In addition, seedless raisins and wine have dominated as processed products. As you can see, these items do not cover all age groups of the population. Grapes can be used to make a variety of high-nutritional items in little quantities.

The biochemical composition of grape elixir. Among such goods, grape elixir is regarded as particularly important. Grape elixir is a natural, non-alcoholic product derived from pure grapes that contains beneficial components and a high concentration of vitamins. It is made up of grape juice that has been directly squeezed. Contains vitamins C, PP, A, B, minerals (P, K, Ca, Fe, Mg), antioxidants (quercetin, catechin), pectin compounds, oils, and polyphenols. The polyphenol concentration of raw materials varies according on the grape variety obtained, ranging from 25 to 45 mg/l and maybe higher. Elixir eco-friendly grape heads and its constituents (seeds, peel, and berry stem). It contains sugar, but no preservatives, alcohol, or flavorings. The color of the prepared grapes will be dark burgundy or dark ruby. Because the components of the grape head were also involved in its technology, its flavor is somewhat taxed and sour-sweet, as is typical of grapes. Elixir's outstanding taste is highlighted by harmony. [1, 2, 6, 7].

Benefits of grape elixir. The grape elixir is not only aromatic, but also extremely beneficial. It boosts the immune system, acts as a powerful preventative against viral infections, raises hemoglobin, enhances memory, normalizes blood cholesterol levels, and rejuvenates the body. Grape elixir dilutes the blood, preventing the formation of thromboses. To give the body with vital elements, humans just need to drink three spoons of elixir every day [1, 2, 6, 7]. Many other scientists have also recognized the outstanding benefits of grape products for human health.

As long as grape juice is the main component of the grape elixir, the seven most popular helpful characteristics are outlined by N.Tkacheva and T. Eliseeva [5] as follows. 1) Grape juice boosts health, digestion, metabolism, and vital tone due to its high glucose, fructose, and antioxidant content. 2) includes various polyphenolic and antioxidant compounds that oxidize the human body and impair its ability to release. 3) Thrombosis must eradicate this pathology, as well as the effects of polyphenolic acids. 4) Drinking a teaspoon of juice before bedtime, which contains melatonin, can increase sleep quality. 5) The juice includes a high concentration of antioxidants, which aid in the treatment of liver and gallbladder disease as well as the cleansing of metal coatings. 6) Grape juice contains carotenoids such as zeaxanthin and lutein, which have been shown to boost favorable effects. 7) Grape juice (particularly black grapes) has a high biochemical content and is an excellent instrument for improving immunity.

Materials and methods.

Rangdor, Saperavi, Cabernet Sauvignon, Khindogni, Pinot Noir (red), Maysky Cherny, and Magarachsky black grape varieties grown in Uzbekistan's Tashkent region Parkent and Kibray district were used to create Grape Elixir. The product was produced in the Laboratory of Tashkent State Agrarian University's Storage and Processing of Agricultural Products Department.

The grapes were frozen for ten hours at -11 to 10 °C to achieve this. After freezing, the grapes and stems were crushed together. At 50–55 °C, the pulp was pasteurized for a duration of 12 hours. The pulp was then heated to a temperature of 65 to 70°C for four hours. Using a refractometer, titrated acidity and pH were determined to monitor the pasteurization process. once the pulp has been pressed.

The temperature range for the wort storage was -2 to -3°C. A ColorLite sph850 spectrophotometer was used to measure the must's color (tab. 1). Two etalon sets—a white acryl etalon and a BAM white ceramic etalon—calibrated the spectrophotometer. For the purpose of reducing noise, each must was used three times per week. The average of the three repetitions per must simple determined the final L*a*b* values. Spectrophotometry measures how light passes through or reflects off the elixir at different wavelengths, allowing precise data collection on the color. This method provides values for the product’s color in systems like the **CIE Lab*** color model, where:

- **L*** represents lightness or darkness,
- **a*** measures the balance between red and green,
- **b*** measures the balance between yellow and blue.

Table 1. Mean L*a*b* colour values of different grape elixir influenced by the two stage pasteurization.

<i>Cultivar</i>	L*	a*	b*
Cabernet sauvignon	59.36	37.27	21.47
Rangdor	58.46	39.27	23.45
Tavkveri	55.65	28.65	34.67
Saperavi	45.55	27.66	23.63
Khindogni	57.12	32.11	21.39
Pino Noir	58.46	39.27	26.15
Mayskiy Cherniy	48.24	29.27	24.45
Magarachskiy	54.46	29.12	34.23

Results.

Anthocyanin coloration, particularly in flowers and fruits where quinoid pigments predominate, may be influenced by pH, copigmentation, and the formation of chelate complexes with metals. At the same time, the nature of the metal is frequently influential. Thus, the anthocyanin complex is purple with molybdenum, blue with iron, and white with nickel and copper. According to the statistics presented above, the relative error of the definitions does not exceed that of the spectrophotometric measurements. The results are fairly reproducible and accurate. This leads us to infer that this technique can be applied to the examination of wines of varied coloration and growing older, and its introduction in Uzbekistan.

As previously stated, grapes are grown in Uzbekistan in copious amounts. And this is "Grape Elixir" polyphenolic drink, which has a wide range of low-cost and precious raw ingredients for production. If the majority of technological grape varieties used to make grape elixir are those that are introduced, then our country has a wide range of black technical grape varieties that are all intended for large-scale farming. Large-scale black technical grape varieties are considered equivalent in our country as long as the majority of the grapes used to make the grape elixir are technical grape types.

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